

Deliverable D5.2.

H&S certification roadmap

Deliverable report

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as consequence of project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allows a close follow up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

Taking social risks and quarry workers into account is especially crucial in WP5, as its specific goals include monitoring health and safety indicators in the production process, as well as and improving health and safety measures in plants.

Table of contents

Deliverable report	3
Document contributors	3
Document history	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of contents	5
List of abbreviations	6
Executive Summary	7
1 Introduction	8
1.1 Deliverable objectives	8
1.2 Intended audience	9
1.3 Structure of the report	9
2 Methodology	9
2.1 Regulation review	9
2.2 Semi-structured stakeholder interviews	10
3 Results	11
3.1 Regulation review	11
3.1.1 EU AI Act	11
3.1.1.1 Summary	11
3.1.1.2 Impact evaluation for applications in quarries	13
3.1.2 EU Data Act	14
3.1.2.1 Summary	14
3.1.2.2 Impact evaluation for applications in quarries	15
3.1.3 EU Cyber Resilience Act	16
3.1.3.1 Summary	16
3.1.3.2 Impact evaluation for applications in quarries	17
3.1.4 EU General Data Protection Regulation	17
3.1.4.1 Summary	18
3.1.4.2 Impact evaluation for applications in quarries	19
3.1.5 Conclusion	19
3.2 Semi-structured stakeholder interviews	20
4 Conclusion and Recommendation	23
4.1 General Roadmap for Safe AI development	23
4.2 Technological roadmap for Safe AI development	25
4.2.1 Design phase	26
4.2.2 Implementation phase	27
4.2.3 Deployment phase	29
4.3 Summary	29
List of Figures	30
List of Tables	30
List of References	31

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DEQ	DigiEcoQuarry
EU	European Union
GA	Grand Agreement
WP	Work package
LTIFR	Lost Time Injury Frequency Rate
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
GPAI	General-Purpose AI
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
B2B	Business-to-Business
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
QM	Quality Management
PM	Project Management
DevOps	Development and Operations
DataOps	Data Operations
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
SAFE®	Scaled Agile Framework®
SPICE	Software Process Improvement and Capability Determination
SIL	Software Integrity Level
MISRA	Motor Industry Software Reliability Association
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Delivery
IT	Information Technology
VUCA	volatile, uncertain, complex, ambiguous

Executive Summary

This deliverable is dedicated to giving insights about strategies towards the increased usage of artificial intelligence in (possibly safety-critical) quarrying use cases.

In this context, we provide an extensive review on regulations and directives adopted by the European Union (EU) which are relevant for development and usage of artificial intelligence in use cases arising in the quarrying context (e.g. EU AI Act, EU Data Act, General Data Protection Regulation, EU Cyber Resilience Act), and give a detailed impact analysis on the quarrying business.

In addition, we conducted 11 semi-structured interviews with relevant stakeholders (quarrying companies, technology providers, industry associations, educational institutions) to gather more insight about actual concerns and barriers, but also about potential drivers regarding the operation of artificial intelligence in quarries.

The found legal, technological and social barriers and drivers are subsequently addressed in a strategic roadmap guiding towards safety AI development in quarrying use cases, where we also give detailed recommendations to stakeholders and present milestones. There, we first give a top-level view on the core drivers and barriers. Second, we provide in-depth technical recommendations and strategies to be used in actual product development projects in order to successfully develop and operate a certified AI system in a safety-critical use case in quarries.

1 Introduction

1.1 Deliverable objectives

The quarrying industry faces significant safety challenges, low accident rate, though the incidents tend to be severe in nature. Mitigating risks and ensuring the well-being of workers and visitors is paramount, as highlighted by various DigiEcoQuarry (DEQ) documents. While existing safety measures at DEQ pilot sites have demonstrably lowered Lost Time Injury Frequency Rates (LTIFRs), concerns persist, particularly regarding interactions between personnel and mobile machinery in shared spaces.

As written in the Grand Agreement (GA) the responsibility with respect to improvements to the occupational safety is within Work Package (WP) 5. In this context, Deliverable 5.1 summarized already several activities (cf. Table 1).

Table 1. Deliverables with activities regarding occupational safety.

Occupational Safety	Lead-Partner	Sites	Deliverable
Interaction between mobile machinery and workers	about, ITK	HOLCIM, VICAT, CIMPOR	3.6 & 5.1
Conveyor belt	SIGMA/UPM	CEMEX, CSI	4.3
Stockpiling with trucks	ITK	CSI	5.1

Having anticipated while writing the GA and being confirmed by the results of the deliverables the usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a great chance to improve the occupational safety inside quarries (cf. Deliverable 5.1). As written in Deliverable 5.1 object recognition with AI is state of the art and has a much greater performance in comparison to deterministic algorithms.

Yet, at the same time, it is observable, not only in DEQ but throughout the (quarry) industry, that the full potential of AI cannot be utilized. For instance, focussing on a scraper system, even though it is most likely more performant than the status quo, it is yet not foreseeable that the scraper will run autonomously, giving an AI-based system the responsibility to monitor the well-functioning and safety of the scraper. Seeing this gap between the great potential of AI and its usage for safety-critical applications, this deliverable shall serve as an attempt to build a bridge between these two points.

The objective is thus to answer the focus question **“What needs to be done so that AI can be used in quarries for safety-critical applications?”** By answering this focus question, the second objective is to outline a roadmap, identifying barriers and give recommendations on how they can be solved.

A roadmap for more safety AI developments is crucial because establishing trust and ensuring the reliable, safe and responsible deployment of AI systems, especially in safety-critical applications, is paramount. Here are several reasons:

Navigating the Evolving Landscape: The field of AI safety is rapidly evolving. Standards, regulations, and best practices are constantly being updated. A roadmap helps developers stay ahead of these changes and ensures their systems meet current and future requirements. This is particularly true for the EU, where new AI regulations are actively being shaped.

Defining Clear Objectives and Milestones: A roadmap breaks down the complex process of safety AI development into manageable steps. It defines clear objectives, milestones, and timelines, allowing developers to track progress, allocate resources effectively, and prioritize tasks. This structured approach is essential for successful certification.

Addressing Specific Safety Concerns: Safety AI development often requires addressing specific safety concerns relevant to the application domain. A roadmap helps developers identify these concerns early on and incorporate appropriate

mitigation strategies into the system design and development process. This proactive approach reduces risks and ensures compliance with safety standards.

Facilitating Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing: A roadmap can serve as a valuable tool for collaboration and knowledge sharing among developers, users, researchers, and regulatory bodies. It promotes a shared understanding of safety requirements and best practices, fostering a collaborative ecosystem for safety AI development.

Reducing Development Costs and Time: By providing a structured approach, a roadmap can help reduce development costs and time. It minimizes rework and ensures efficient use of resources, leading to faster and more cost-effective development. This is a vital concern for projects like DEQ operating within specific funding constraints.

1.2 Intended audience

The dissemination level of this deliverable is public.

1.3 Structure of the report

This deliverable is split into four parts: (1) Introduction, (2) Methodology, (3) Results and (4) Conclusion and Recommendation. In the next chapter, the methodology will be introduced starting with an overview on relevant EU regulations and directives regarding AI and adjacent fields. Subsequently, we describe the method of the conducted semi-structured stakeholder interviews which comprise the second element of our methodology for this deliverable. Similarly, the results section consists of two parts: first, we give a detailed overview on the content of the most relevant AI and Data legislations (e.g. the EU AI Act) and analyse their impact on innovative quarrying systems. Second, we summarize the results of the conducted interviews. The final chapter of this deliverable is concerned with the outline of a roadmap for safety AI development.

2 Methodology

2.1 Regulation review

Like other laws and regulation does the access and use of data as well as the development and use of AI take place on different layers of regulation (see Figure 1 below).

Figure 1: Layers of regulation.

For the purpose of this deliverable only EU legislation has been considered. Specifically, under the European Union’s Strategy for Data, several legislative acts have been adopted regulating the development and placing on the market of digital products and services:

Table 2. Legislative acts adopted by the EU with respect to data, AI and digital products.

Regulation	Description	In scope for quarry industry
AI Act	Contains regulations for development and deployment of AI and AI systems	Yes
Data Act	Concerned with establishing product data access for users and other parties	Yes
Cyber Resilience Act	Creates a framework of cybersecurity requirements for the entire lifecycle of digital products	Yes
General Data Protection Regulation	Comprehensive data protection regulation aimed to safeguard personal data and privacy rights of individuals	Yes
Product Liability Directive, AI Liability Directive (proposal)	Fault-free liability for defective software (incl. AI systems) Comprehensive procedural disclosure requirements (also for national tort claims) Comprehensive facilitation of evidence for plaintiffs	Yes – legislation pending
Data Governance Act	Creates a framework for e.g. voluntary data sharing, reuse of public sector data, intermediary data service providers	No
Digital Markets Act	Concerned with competition and antitrust issues for big technology platforms	No
Digital Services Act	Concerned with harmful or illegal goods, services and online content	No

Regarding – possibly safety-related – applications in quarries, the relevance of the acts mentioned above is different. In a nutshell, the Digital Markets Act only applies to big technology platforms (e.g. Amazon, Apple) and the Digital Services Act has a strong focus on online services. The Data Governance Act is also seen not in scope for quarrying systems since its core obligations are for public sector bodies and data service providers. On the other hand, since an innovative quarrying system is likely to include the use of AI, processes data to some extent and might consist of multiple connected components, the AI and Data Acts, together with the General Data Protection Regulation are to be taken into account. Furthermore, the Cyber Resilience Act concerned with digital products including a data connection is to be considered as well. The product liability directive (adopted by EU Council and Parliament) and AI liability directive (in proposal state) must also be observed. These guidelines govern the fault-independent liability for defective software (including AI systems). The aim is to create an EU-wide uniform level of protection for damage caused by AI systems. The introduction of the new liability rules (which are strongly connected to the regulations from the AI Act) will promote trusted AI systems, ensure their benefits to the internal market and reduce legal uncertainty about the liability risk for companies. Since these two directives still have to be substantiated by national laws, we do not consider them in the following.

In the result section, we focus more in detail on those acts having a major impact on development and operation of a digitized quarry system.

2.2 Semi-structured stakeholder interviews

Given the complexities of safety AI development and its evolving landscape, semi-structured interviews with stakeholders in the DEQ project are essential for several reasons:

Capturing diverse perspectives: Semi-structured interviews allow to gather insights from a wide range of stakeholders, including quarry operators, workers, safety experts, AI developers, and regulatory bodies. Each group brings unique perspectives and experiences related to quarry safety, AI adoption, and certification requirements. This wide range of understanding is crucial for developing a comprehensive and effective roadmap.

Exploring context-specific challenges: Quarry operations and safety considerations vary depending on the specific context. Semi-structured interviews allow us to delve into the unique challenges and opportunities present at each DEQ pilot sites, ensuring that the roadmap addresses context-specific safety concerns and is practically applicable across diverse environments. This tailored approach is critical for success.

Uncovering unforeseen issues and solutions: The open-ended nature of semi-structured interviews allows stakeholders to raise unforeseen issues and potential solutions that might not be captured with other methods. This iterative feedback process strengthens the roadmap by identifying potential roadblocks and incorporating valuable insights from those directly involved in quarry operations. This “ground-truthing” process is invaluable.

Understanding user needs and acceptance factors: Semi-structured interviews are valuable for understanding user needs and acceptance factors related to AI-powered safety systems. This information can be used to design user-friendly systems and training programs, promoting user adoption and maximizing the effectiveness of the safety intervention. This “human-centered” approach is key.

To ensure a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities related to safe AI development within the quarrying industry, all organizations participating in the DEQ project were approached regarding their perspectives on this crucial topic. A series of semi-structured interviews has been conducted, resulting in valuable insights from a diverse range of stakeholders. With the explicit permission of the interviewees, a total of 9 oral interviews were recorded, whereas 2 interviews were based on written answers to questions. Subsequently these answers were analysed to inform the development of a robust and practical roadmap for safety AI development. This qualitative data provides a rich foundation for addressing context-specific safety concerns and ensuring the successful integration of AI-powered safety solutions within the quarrying environment.

3 Results

3.1 Regulation review

In this section, we analyse more in detail the EU regulations regarding data and AI which we see in scope for an innovative quarrying system (cf. Table 3). Each legislative act is first summarized focussing on the obligations arising for enterprises in general, and second with a more particular regard on the quarrying use cases.

3.1.1 EU AI Act

The EU Artificial Intelligence (AI) act is a regulation on and sets a framework for development and deployment of AI and AI systems in the EU. AI systems and models are classified, and hence regulated, according to the risk for their users.

3.1.1.1 Summary

The scope of the EU AI Act is broad with respect to the techniques seen as “AI”. Its territorial validity is not limited to the EU since it can apply to providers and deployers from non-EU countries. Some specific use cases are not covered by the EU AI Act.

Table 3. Scope of the EU AI Act.

Technical	Territorial	By purpose
<p>Broad definition of “AI system”: “...means a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments.” (AI Act Art.3(1))</p>	<p>Broad territorial scope: applies to Providers (AI developers) making AI systems or models available in the EU, Deployers (professional AI users) that are EU-based, Providers and deployers if AI output is used in the EU.</p>	<p>Limited exemptions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Military, defence, national security, law enforcement, judicial cooperation ▪ Scientific purposes, R&D activities ▪ Personal non-professional activities ▪ Open source (partly) ▪ High-risk AI products or safety components covered by special harmonized safety legislation (e.g. aviation, vehicles, rail, <u>not</u> machines) – delegated acts pending

Depending on their specific use-case, AI systems are classified as high-risk or even prohibited to make available. On the technical side, general purpose AI (GPAI) models with a high impact capability are seen to pose a systemic risk and hence are regulated more strongly.

Table 4. Definition and risk classification of AI in connection with the regulations contained in the AI Act.

	Definition/Classification	Examples/Use cases
Prohibited AI	AI used for manipulative, exploitative and social control practices. Limited exceptions exist for specific use cases	Social scoring, predictive policing, emotion recognition at workplace or education
High-risk AI in connection with harmonized safety legislation based on EU New Legislative Framework	Products or safety components covered by special harmonized safety legislation (cf. AI Act Annex I(A)) and necessary third-party conformity assessment	Machinery, lifts, personal protective equipment, medical devices, toys
High-risk AI not covered by harmonized safety legislation	AI systems with specific use cases (cf. AI Act Annex III) posing a high risk on health, safety or fundamental rights	Biometrics, critical infrastructure, education, employment
High-risk AI in connection with other harmonized safety legislation	Products or safety components covered by special harmonized safety legislation (cf. AI Act Annex I(B))	Aviation, vehicles and their systems and components, rail
AI systems with additional transparency obligations	Apply for AI systems directly interacting with individuals and/or generating content	Chatbots, Image creators
GPAI models	AI models with significant generality and capability for many distinct tasks	GPT, Stable Diffusion, DALL-E
GPAI models with systemic risk	GPAI with high impact capability (i.e. high amount of computation used for model training) or directly classified as such by EU lawmakers	

Whereas those AI systems which are viewed as a clear threat to health, safety and rights are prohibited, those AI systems and models that pose high or system risks are permitted but extensively regulated as shown by the requirements below.

Table 5. Requirements for providers and deployers according to the AI Act

	Requirements on providers	Requirements on deployers	Enforcement date
Prohibited AI	Must not be made available	Must not be used	02 Feb 2025
High-risk AI in connection with harmonized safety legislation based on EU New Legislative Framework	Risk management; Data and data governance; Technical documentation; Keeping of records; Transparency and provision of information to deployers; Make human oversight possible; Demonstrate high level of accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity; Quality management; Conformity assessment, declaration of conformity and CE marking; Registration in EU database; Cooperation with regulatory authorities; Comply with EU accessibility requirements.	Run AI system according to instructions of use; Implement human oversight; Keeping of records; Monitoring; Transparency and notification; Cooperation with regulatory authorities; Assessment of input data quality and data protection impact (where applicable); Assessment of fundamental rights impact (in specific cases). Note: deployers can be subject to the providers' obligations, e.g. if the system or its intended purpose are modified.	02 Aug 2027
High-risk AI not covered by harmonized safety legislation			02 Aug 2026
High-risk AI in connection with other harmonized safety legislation	Unclear yet – delegated acts pending	Unclear yet – delegated acts pending	
AI systems with additional transparency obligations	Ensure that users are informed; Mark content as generated by AI.	Disclose that content being deep fake or relevant for public interest is generated by AI.	02 Aug 2026
GPAI models	Publish summary on used training data; Technical documentation; Documentation for downstream providers. Policy to comply with EU copyright and IP laws. Exemption for open-source models.	-	02 Aug 2025
GPAI models with systemic risk	Requirements for GPAI models apply without exemption. Additionally: model evaluation; adversarial testing; risk management; reporting of serious incidents; ensuring cybersecurity; notification of EU body.	-	02 Aug 2025

3.1.1.2 Impact evaluation for applications in quarries

To assess the impact of the EU AI Act on the development and operating an innovative quarrying system, we first analyse the definition of “AI system” given in the act more in detail. It is very broad, and its limitations are restricted, e.g. the adaptiveness of the AI system is not even compulsory. Therefore, also basic machine learning algorithms (e.g. regression)

fall into the category of AI systems. Furthermore, machine learning, classical statistics and data science cannot be distinguished incisively. We expect that the legal interpretation will be very wide. Hence, in-depth-knowledge of the used methods and algorithms in the digital components is necessary, both for providers (e.g. software development companies) and deployers (e.g. quarrying enterprises). Even if not required legally, complying to standard software and product development processes is recommended. Building up basic knowledge about artificial intelligence in enterprises developing and using digital products also is a driver for innovation. There are many use cases for AI, as we see here in the quarrying ecosystem, which might not have yet been considered by the respective companies because of lack of knowledge.

Regarding a possibly time-consuming and cost-intensive certification process according to the AI Act, it is crucial to evaluate if the developed AI system falls into the high-risk category (we see it unlikely that prohibited AI or GPAI models are developed in the quarrying context). Specifically, it is likely that the AI use cases are covered by harmonized safety legislations. Hence, it is needed to evaluate if the AI system is a safety component. For example, a person-detection AI component in automatic scraper systems (as considered in this project) can in principle be seen as a safety-relevant machinery component and therefore be classified as high-risk AI. On the other hand, the introduction of a non-AI fallback or redundancy system can prevent the system to be classified as safety component. Such redundancy or fallback can be achieved e.g. by human oversight and using the AI output not directly for an autonomous decision and reaction of the system but mainly using the output as a supportive element for human decision.

Figure 2: Main findings and recommendations from the EU AI Act.

Nevertheless, several process elements and artifacts which are compulsory in the high-risk case are also important in the non-high-risk case in order to achieve high product quality, e.g. quality and risk management, data governance, cybersecurity or documentation. Complementing the AI Act, the EU Data Act and the EU Cyber Resilience Act even explicitly require those for some use cases. Still, the regulatory affairs leading to a – possibly third-party – conformity assessment may be a cost driver and should be avoided where possible.

By delegated acts (which are being developed from now on), the EU also might enforce some additional or deviating regulations for the use cases where harmonized safety legislation exists which is not based on the EU New Legislative framework. The AI Act only applies here in an indirect way. This unclear state could be a barrier for innovation as it is also unclear when these delegated acts will be in force. Regarding the quarrying ecosystem, this could hold e.g. for heavy-duty vehicles (such as trucks) which fall under the EU vehicle regulation for on-highway vehicles. For vehicles mainly used on construction sites and quarries, the EU machine regulation – and hence directly the AI Act – could be applicable.

3.1.2 EU Data Act

The EU Data Act sets regulatory requirements for establishing data access for users and other parties, e.g. to make possible their re-use for other purposes.

3.1.2.1 Summary

The data in scope is that of *connected products* and their *related services*. A **connected product** “obtains, generates or collects data concerning its use or environment and that is able to communicate product data via an electronic

communications service, physical connection or on-device access” (Data Act Art. 2(6)). **Related services** are services which are crucial for the functionality of the connected product or have subsequently been connected with the product to add to, update or adapt its functions (cf. Data Act Art. 2(7)).

The core regulations of the EU Data Act are as follows:

Table 6. Core regulations for manufacturers, data holders and users contained in the Data Act.

Obligation to make data accessible to the user (Art. 3)	<p>Data including relevant metadata must be easily, securely, free of charge, in a comprehensive, structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and directly (where relevant and technically feasible) accessible to the user (cf. Data Act Art 3(1)).</p> <p>User must be informed in advance of purchase or contracting about e.g. the nature of the data, the data generating and storing capabilities of the product and how to access the data.</p> <p>Enforcement date: 12 Sep 2026</p>
Rights and obligations of users and data holders about access, use and making available data (Art. 4)	<p>Data holders are obliged to make data available to users or third parties upon request of the user.</p>
Right of the user to share data with third parties (Art. 5)	<p>Exemptions are possible for safety or security purposes as well as to protect trade secrets.</p> <p>Processing the data is only allowed as agreed with the user and according to personal data protection law.</p> <p>Users and third parties are prohibited to use or share the data in order to develop a competitive product.</p> <p>All parties shall not use the data to derive – e.g. economic – insights about one another.</p>

Additionally, data holders must make data available to the **public sector** in case of an **exceptional need**, e.g. a public emergency or in public interest (cf. Data Act Ch. V).

Exemptions of the regulations apply to **small and medium-sized** enterprises (SMEs, cf. Data Act Arts. 7(1),15(2)), whereas **additional requirements** exist for **big technology platforms** (cf. Data Act Art. 5(3)).

For the provision of data in business-to-business relations, a **compensation** can be agreed upon. However, if the data recipient is an SME, a non-profit research organisation or the public sector in case of a public emergency, the compensation may only cover the costs or must be omitted completely (cf. Data Act Arts. 9,20).

3.1.2.2 Impact evaluation for applications in quarries

In an innovative quarrying system, there are many components that fall under the category of connected products. For example, a mobile machine with sensors gathering data about itself, other machines or materials, is an IoT device and thus a connected product in the sense of the Data Act. The Data Act’s requirement to make device data accessible by design hence enforces manufacturers to take this feature into account from the very start of product development (e.g. at the design stage). Manufacturers and downstream data-holders might also be required to provide data to product users (which will mainly be in a business-to-business (B2B) context in the case of quarries) and thus must set up the respective processes. All in all, this could constitute a time and cost factor for the affected enterprises.

On the other hand, data availability can be a major driver for innovation, such as the development of further data processing services by re-using already accessible data. For software development and engineering companies, this might create additional business opportunities.

Figure 3: Main findings and recommendations from the EU Data Act.

The Data Act also strengthens data protection principles, e.g. safeguarding of personal data (in connection with the General Data Protection Regulation), data minimization (data that is already available does not need to be generated again) and security. If data provision threatens product safety or security, it can be disregarded (with certain legal obligations).

3.1.3 EU Cyber Resilience Act

3.1.3.1 Summary

The EU Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) creates a framework of cybersecurity requirements for the entire lifecycle (including a support period which is no less than five years) of **products with digital elements** (with respect to **software, hardware and remote data processing**). It enters into force in the last quarter of 2024 (act has been adopted on 10 Oct 2024, formal entry into force pending) such that the main obligations for manufacturers, importers and distributors are enforced in 2026 and 2027.

The act applies to digital products the use of which includes a **data connection** to a device or network, with the exception of some use cases (e.g. medical products, vehicles except for agriculture and forestry, aviation, identical spare parts) or purposes (e.g. national security, no commercial activity), cf. CRA Art. 2.

Manufacturers of digital products in scope are obliged to meet the following **general requirements** (cf. CRA Arts. 6,13,14):

- **Essential cybersecurity requirements** (cf. CRA Annex I(I)), e.g.
 - No known exploitable vulnerabilities.
 - Existence of a secure by default configuration.
 - Possibility of security updates.
 - Protection from unauthorised access.
 - Protection of data confidentiality and integrity.
 - Data minimisation according to intended purpose of the product.
 - Protection of the basic functions of the product, also after an incident.
 - Minimization of the negative impact of incidents.
 - Recording and monitoring internal activity relevant for security.
 - Possibility for data removal by the user.
- Installed **security updates**.
- Cybersecurity **risk assessment**.
- **Technical documentation**.
- **Information** for the user.
- **Reporting** of vulnerabilities and incidents.
- **Declaration of conformity** and CE marking.

Additionally, digital products are classified according to their criticality to other products and services or to the user. The main consequence of a higher criticality class on the manufacturer’s requirements is a higher level of necessary conformity assessment. The classification can be changed via delegated acts of the EU Commission (cf. CRA Arts. 7,8).

Table 7. Criticality classification (cf. CRA Arts. 7,8, Annexes III,IV) and impact on conformity assessment procedure (cf. CRA Art. 32).

Criticality class	Examples	Needed level of conformity assessment
Default (no criticality)	Consumer devices, standard software. Note: this class comprises almost all use cases.	Self-assessment
Important Class I	Browsers, password managers, smart home devices	Self-assessment of the application of harmonised standards (where existing) or third-party assessment
Important Class II	Firewalls, tamper-resistant microcontrollers	Third-party assessment
Critical	Smart meter, smartcards	European cybersecurity certificate at assurance level at least “substantial”

3.1.3.2 Impact evaluation for applications in quarries

The scope of the Cyber Resilience Act is similar to that of the AI and Data Acts. Like in the Data Act, IoT products and services are subject to the Cyber Resilience Act since they contain data connections which require cybersecurity protection. Vehicles are exempt, like in the AI Act, but requirements with respect to security are handled in the respective harmonized standards, e.g. the EU vehicle regulation. On the other hand, machines (also including construction site and quarrying vehicles, if appropriate) are covered by the Cyber Resilience Act. In general, an innovative quarrying system consisting of several connected IoT products and platforms exhibits cybersecurity risks which need to be mitigated. The cybersecurity measures and the essential cybersecurity requirements proposed in the Cyber Resilience Act are seen to be useful and relevant regardless of the explicit legal coverage of the respective use-case. For product manufacturers, the implementation of cyber security measures can also be an indirect business driver by adding value to products and thus increasing the customer confidence.

Figure 4: Main findings and recommendations from the EU Cyber Resilience Act.

Concerning required conformity assessment processes and artifacts according to the Cyber Resilience Act, it is very likely that the use cases in a quarrying ecosystem are classified as non-critical. Hence, only a more lightweight self-assessment for conformity is required.

3.1.4 EU General Data Protection Regulation

The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is aimed at the protection of the fundamental rights of natural persons (called *data subjects*) with respect to the protection of their personal data.

3.1.4.1 Summary

The following **main principles** of personal data processing apply:

Table 8. Principles relating to processing of personal data (cf. GDPR Art. 5(1)).

Lawfulness, Fairness and Transparency	Processing shall be lawful, fair and transparent in relation to the data subject.
Purpose limitation	Data collection shall be for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes only.
Data minimisation	Processed data shall be adequate, relevant and limited to what is needed.
Accuracy	Data shall be accurate and up to date, incorrect data must be corrected without delay.
Storage limitation	Data storage in a form permitting identification of the data subject is only allowed as long as it is necessary.
Integrity and Confidentiality	Measures must be taken to ensure data security and prevent data loss, destruction or damage.

Personal data processing on behalf of the *controller* (i.e. the responsible entity) is only considered as lawful if one of the following **conditions** is fulfilled (cf. GDPR Art. 6(1)):

- **Consent** is given.
- **Necessity** for fulfilment or of entering into a contract.
- Compliance with **a legal obligation**.
- Necessity for protection of **vital interests**.
- Necessity for exercise of **official authority** or a task in **public interest**.
- Purpose of **legitimate interest** of the controller (if not overridden by the data subject's interests or rights).

The central **rights of the data subjects** regarding the processing of their personal data are as follows.

Table 9. Rights of the data subject (cf. GDPR Ch. III).

Information	Information on what, how and why data is processed and stored, the identity of the controller and on the data subject's rights.
Access	Access to the personal data held by the controller.
Rectification	Correction of inaccurate data and completion of incomplete data.
Erasure	Erasure of personal data in certain circumstances, e.g. withdrawn consent, ended necessity or unlawful processing.
Restriction of processing	Limited processing in certain circumstances, e.g. when data accuracy is contested.
Portability	Provided data is in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and can be easily transmitted to another controller.
Objection	Data subjects may object to data processing in many situations.
Refusal of automated decision-making	Data subjects may object to undergo automated decision making or profiling in certain situations.

Proportionate and in respect of the fundamental rights, the obligations derived from these rights can be restricted by law in certain circumstances, e.g. to protect national and public security (cf. GDPR Art. 23).

Regarding the data protection mechanisms themselves as well as the exercise of the data subjects' rights, controller and processor are bound by the following **obligations** (amongst others):

- Implementation of **technical and organisational measures** regarding data-protection, e.g. (cf. GDPR Arts. 25,32)
 - **pseudonymisation** and **encryption**.
 - **confidentiality, integrity, availability** and **resilience** of processing systems and services.
 - **restore availability** and **access** in case of an incident.

- a process for regularly **testing, assessing** and **evaluating** the effectiveness of the implemented measures.
- Maintenance of **records** of data processing activities (cf. GDPR Art. 30).
- **Assessment of data protection impact** in high-risk use cases such as automated profiling or systematic large-scale monitoring of a public area (cf. GDPR Art. 35).
- Implementation of **processes regarding the data subjects’ consent and rights** (including transparency and easy means of communication, cf. GDPR Art. 12).
- Designation of a **data protection officer** (cf. GDPR Ch. IV(4)).
- **Notification** of a personal data breach to the supervisory authority (cf. GDPR Art. 33) and to the data subject (cf. GDPR Art. 34).

3.1.4.2 Impact evaluation for applications in quarries

In quarries, data from IoT sensors (e.g. in machines, vehicles) or business data can possibly be relevant for the GDPR. For example, an object detection system with sensors (e.g. cameras) generates image data containing images of natural persons annotated with metadata (e.g. timestamps). As these are seen as personal data, the obligations of the GDPR apply. In this case, data processing should be made transparent to the on-site workers and explicit consent should be obtained.

In addition, data governance processes are required by the GDPR, such as a data assessment to provide in-depth-knowledge about the data which is processed during product deployment and operation. Being the cornerstone of EU data protection law, the scope of the GDPR is not affected by the other acts described in this section.

Figure 5: Main findings and recommendations from the GDPR.

3.1.5 Conclusion

On manufacturers, but also on operators, the EU acts presented in this section pose a variety of obligations regarding the use and protection of data in many use cases. The core principles are as follows:

Table 10. Core data principles.

Data governance, data processing, data quality	Setting standards of how to gather, process and store data, also with respect to data quality (e.g. as needed for high-quality AI model development)
Data protection, data security	Governance of data access, with particular regard to personal data protection and cyber security
Data accessibility	Making product data accessible to the user by design

Even if the initial setup of these principles might be a cost factor, we see several long-term potentials arising. For example, data governance is an enabler for maximal findability and (re-)usability of data, thus generating additional business opportunities. Especially for AI systems development, data assessment processes leading to higher data quality (such as completeness, accuracy, consistency) will subsequently yield a higher product quality and added value. It is important that the mentioned principles are taken in mind right from the start of product development. Setting up data governance standards for customers in a B2B relationship will bring more business prospects for consulting and data engineering companies.

In addition, product manufacturers are often subject to regulatory and quality management processes according to the described EU acts, e.g.

Table 11. Regulatory affairs and quality management.

Risk management	Assessment and mitigation of risks originating in cyber vulnerability, data safeguarding, safety or other influences from AI
Quality management	Standards and processes for e.g. data management, software development and product management
Documentation (e.g. technical, customer)	Provision of suitable documentation for the relevant stakeholders (e.g. customers, users, authorities)
Conformity	Ensuring conformity with the aforementioned acts by assessment and drawing up a declaration of conformity

All in all, the need to analyse and possible adapt existing processes can be a driver for higher quality and more cost efficiency.

In general, it is important to build up knowledge about the relevant legislation, norms and standards (e.g. the regulations summarized here, but also adjacent acts like harmonized standards), and to keep this knowledge up to date. Due to the dynamic environment regarding AI and data, much is still in the air – some legislation is pending, and new legislation is conceivable. Missing key facts could lead to a high increase of costs and needed time during the product development process. Again, consulting and engineering companies can provide the necessary in-depth and technical knowledge to support manufacturers in adherence to the respective legal obligations.

3.2 Semi-structured stakeholder interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with a representative subset of the organizations participating in DEQ to gather diverse perspectives on the challenges and opportunities related to (safe) AI development. A total of 11 out of the 25 participating organizations were interviewed, including 5 quarry operators, 3 technology providers, 2 universities and one industry association. The interviews were anonymized to encourage an open dialogue and protect confidential information and business practices of the participating organizations. Please note, that these results cannot be generalized to all quarries, technology providers and connected stakeholders. However, they give nevertheless a certain direction, which was observable during the interviews.

The interviews conducted provided valuable insights into the multifaceted perspectives within the quarrying industry. The analysis of the interviews revealed distinct social, technological, and legal barriers and drivers:

Social Barriers:

- **Resistance to Change:** Difficulty to integrate AI into established processes, operator hesitancy towards new technologies, and prioritization of immediate production over long-term innovation create resistance to change.
- **Lack of Knowledge and Training:** Limited understanding of the capabilities and benefits of AI amongst quarry personnel, coupled with a lack of targeted training programs, hinders effective implementation. Fear of digital interfaces also contributes to this barrier.
- **Communication Gaps:** Insufficient communication between technology providers and quarry operators regarding AI solutions and their potential benefits can impede adoption. Clear communication about the purpose and impact of AI systems is crucial for user acceptance.
- **Job Displacement Concerns:** Automation through AI can raise concerns about potential job displacement among quarry workers, creating resistance to adoption.

Social Drivers:

- **Next Generation Workforce:** Younger employees' interest in technology and digital tools can be a significant driver for AI adoption.

- **Increased Awareness and Education:** Raising awareness about AI successes in similar industries and providing targeted training programs can promote acceptance and empower quarry personnel to utilize AI effectively.
- **Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing:** Fostering collaboration between technology providers and quarry operators enables knowledge sharing and promotes a better understanding of specific quarry needs and potential AI solutions.

Technological Barriers:

- **Data Availability and Quality:** Limited access to relevant data, data quality issues, and the absence of standardized data formats hinder AI model training and validation. OEM data restrictions and reluctance to share data among quarries exacerbate this challenge.
- **Customization Needs:** The diverse nature of quarry operations and the lack of standardized processes require costly and time-consuming customization of AI solutions.
- **Challenging Environmental Conditions:** The rough environmental conditions (e.g. dust, vibration, network) limits the usage of hardware, software and systems considerable.
- **Lack of Available Solutions:** The limited availability of ready-to-deploy, quarry-specific AI solutions from technology providers restricts implementation options. Reliance on second-hand machinery often limits sensor integration possibilities.
- **Integration Complexity:** Integrating AI systems into existing quarry infrastructure and workflows can be complex, requiring specialized expertise and potentially disrupting existing operations.
- **Cybersecurity Concerns:** Increased reliance on connected systems and data sharing raises concerns about potential cybersecurity vulnerabilities and the need for robust system resilience.

Technological Drivers:

- **Retrofitting Opportunities:** Retrofitting existing machinery with AI-enabled sensors and systems can present a practical pathway for enhancing safety and optimizing existing processes.
- **Growing Data Availability:** As data collection and storage practices mature, the increasing availability of quarry-specific data can fuel the development of more effective AI models.
- **Potential for improved Safety, Efficiency, and Productivity:** The potential for AI to reduce human error, automate hazardous tasks, enable predictive maintenance, and improve overall quarry efficiency and productivity are strong drivers for adoption.

Legal Barriers:

- **Limited Awareness of Regulations:** Low awareness and understanding of relevant regulations like the AI Act, Data Act, and Cyber Resilience Act create uncertainty and hinder proactive compliance efforts. This lack of awareness extends to the implications of these regulations for data handling, liability, and certification processes.
- **Unclear Certification Processes:** Lack of clear guidelines and established standards for safety AI certification in the quarrying sector create ambiguity and can discourage investment in AI solutions.
- **Undefined Liability Frameworks:** Uncertainty regarding liability in the event of accidents involving AI-powered systems poses a significant legal barrier to adoption.

Stakeholder-specific perspectives:

- **Quarry Operators:** While acknowledging the potential of AI for safety and optimization, operators emphasized practical challenges like limited resources, the need for user-friendly interfaces, and concerns from workers about job displacement. Uncertainty about data sharing, liability in case of accidents, and a lack of familiarity with the capabilities of AI further contribute to their hesitation. It was highlighted that the dynamic quarry environment could be seen as a key driver for AI adoption.
- **Technology Providers:** These stakeholders focused on data availability and quality as major roadblocks. They stressed the importance of close collaboration with quarries for customization and addressing varying technology proficiency levels among quarry personnel. There is from the technology provider the view, that the industry's move towards digitalization is there, helping obviously to make more use of AI. This can only be done with training and user-friendly systems. However, there are considerable concerns regarding unclear certification requirements and the potential burden of overly stringent cybersecurity measures.

- **Universities:** Universities highlighted the technical complexities and opportunities, noting the diversity of quarry operations as a challenge for scalability. They stressed the need for easy-to-use AI tools, increased awareness, and targeted training. Moreover, affordability and validation challenges need to be considered.
- **Industry association:** According to the interview, one concern is the existing workforce culture, particularly amongst older workers, who are more likely to be resistant to adopting new technologies and changing established practices. This is compounded by a lack of available training and a skills gap related to AI. From a technological standpoint, unreliable network infrastructure and limited connectivity at quarry sites create significant hurdles for implementing data-driven AI solutions. Data availability and integration issues, along with the prevalence of isolated systems, further impede AI development and deployment. Cybersecurity vulnerabilities are also a growing concern. Legally, outdated regulations and the absence of clear AI-specific provisions in existing (and currently drafted) frameworks create uncertainty and hinder innovation. Despite these challenges, the association recognizes the transformative potential of AI for simplifying processes, improving productivity, and positively impacting the economy. They see significant opportunities in leveraging the enthusiasm of a motivated, typically younger segment of the workforce. To accelerate AI adoption, the association emphasizes the need for upskilling and training programs, along with demonstrating the tangible benefits of AI through industry success stories. Collaboration with policymakers to modernize regulations and provide clear guidelines for AI implementation, particularly regarding safety certification, is viewed as crucial for unlocking the full potential of AI in the quarrying industry.

Addressing these interconnected social, technological, and legal barriers and leveraging the corresponding drivers is crucial for developing a successful roadmap for safe AI development in the quarrying industry. The roadmap should promote education and training, facilitate collaboration, encourage the development of user-friendly and quarry-specific solutions, address data access and sharing concerns, and provide clear guidance on navigating the evolving regulatory landscape.

4 Conclusion and Recommendation

This chapter is dedicated to a summary of the obtained results and to the outline of a roadmap towards safe AI development. Our proposed roadmap is twofold: first, we present a general roadmap addressing social, technological and legal barriers and drivers for stakeholders in general. The second part of our roadmap is concerned with a more in-detail analysis of technological and procedural risks in product development and gives recommendations on the conduct of projects.

4.1 General Roadmap for Safe AI development

For addressing general social, legal and technological recommendations, we identify three major stakeholders:

- **Educational institutions**, e.g. schools, universities, community colleges, popular science resources.
- **Policy makers**, e.g. EU commission and parliament, national governments and legislatures, trade unions.
- **Enterprises**, e.g. technology and engineering providers, quarrying operators.

For each stakeholder, we see target visions and tasks that will be described in the following (cf. Figure 6). Most of our recommendations are targeted towards (social, occupational, entrepreneurial) acceptance of AI because most of the barriers and drivers mentioned in the stakeholder interviews are going into that direction. Nevertheless, our identified stakeholder targets can be divided into three main categories:

- **Knowledge and learning**: build knowledge about AI among the public and in companies.
- **Legislation and standardization**: complete necessary legislation, foster the establishment of standards (e.g. for data).
- **Business and occupation**: support entrepreneurial transformation and innovation, enable collaboration between companies and business units, establish and keep a good work environment for employees and workers.

Figure 6: Social roadmap targeting safety AI development.

We now elaborate on our recommendations more in detail.

Inform and make aware: For increasing AI acceptance by the quarry workers, knowledge is crucial. Whereas AI is a present factor in many social and political activities, awareness and facts about the capabilities, risks, but also about the benefits of AI do not seem to have reached all parts of industry. Educational institutions for all ages, as well as relevant media, could focus more strongly on informing the stakeholders, e.g. by public information campaigns and projects in mining schools and in mining courses at universities. It is of major importance that these activities are tailored in such a way that all parts of the quarrying workforce are reached, independent of age or educational background.

Foster learning: Together with increasing general AI awareness, dedicated training opportunities for different target audiences among the quarrying and engineering workforce and management help to improve AI. There exists already a huge variety of courses and trainings on (e.g. online) learning platforms. However, they often are dedicated to (experienced) software developers, not to a broader audience. For small or medium-sized quarrying enterprises, there is certainly a lack of high-level, management-orientated training formats about AI. In addition, it is needed that the companies create more learning opportunities for their employees. We think that continuous learning (not restricted to technical fields) is important for business and employee development. With that, concerns about the disruption created by AI (e.g. fear of job loss) can additionally be reduced.

Share success stories: From an entrepreneurial point of view, acceptance of AI (and hence, extension or transformation of business models and processes) depends on the expected return of invest. In our opinion, sharing success stories, internally and even to the public, is essential. This can also raise leads or opportunities and enhances the collaboration between quarrying companies and technology providers.

Foster collaboration: Collaboration between companies (e.g. between quarrying enterprises and technology providers), but also between business units and teams in enterprises (e.g. between system developers, IT department and product users such as quarry workers), is crucial in VUCA (volatile, uncertain, complex, ambiguous) environments. Besides technical and non-technical expertise, effective and clear communication is of major importance when it comes to collaboration. Respecting the individual expertise and addressing the needs, expectations and goals of one another, a streamlined collaboration is conceivable where the drive for results is the central focus. Besides B2B or business activities, a setup of informal collaboration channels in companies enhances knowledge sharing and communication and thus brings a positive and cooperative corporate culture where everybody is able to contribute to the success of the company. Start with small (passive) AI use cases, which do not intervene too much into the daily working routine of the employees. In a broader context, legal policy makers in connection with e.g. trade unions can create the respective framework conditions for labour. On company level (e.g. in quarrying enterprises), corporate directives and labour-management contracts can implement these conditions (and can even set additional standards) to add to trust and acceptance of digital processes by the (quarry) workers which is the basis for successful collaboration.

Support innovation: To ease and foster innovative safe AI activities in business, the public sector can invest in programs for the economy stimulating these activities. DEQ serves here as a good example for the quarrying industry. Apart from that, companies can foster innovation by giving every employee the possibility to share ideas – by creating innovation platforms and in general, by having a positive mindset towards new ideas, change and transformation. It is important to hear the needs and ideas on all levels of workforce: the feedback from the actual daily users of a product, application or machine (e.g. a quarrying worker operating a quarrying machine) is invaluable.

Remove legal uncertainty: Even if the new regulations concerning AI, data and connected products can serve as a driver by setting standards and enabling data-driven innovation, the uncertainties due to pending or unclear legislation are hindering for quarrying companies regarding AI development and usage. These roadblocks shall be removed in a timely manner in order to unleash the full potential of, e.g. the EU's strategy for data.

Support standards: Standardization of processes and data formats is a key element for streamlining product development and collaboration of different stakeholders. Policy makers, such as the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO) or business associations can collaborate with scientific institutions to generate more and also to review and adapt existing standards. To this end, quarrying and engineering companies are in need to be up to date about existing standards and have to incorporate these into their own processes and methods.

4.2 Technological roadmap for Safe AI development

On a deeper, technological level, we propose a roadmap for safety AI development which is based on a two-dimensional approach (see Figure 7 below):

- (1) **Time:** our recommendations are related to typical phases in the development of smart products, putting several milestones. We distinguish between the following phases:
 - a. **Design** phase: processes and collaboration models are set up; competence is built; important design considerations are undertaken.
 - b. **Implementation** phase: actual product development including the achievement of certification until finally, the product is placed on the market.
 - c. **Deployment** phase: product available on the market; necessary improvements to be done; monitoring and request handling according to legal requirements; re-use considerations in order to generate additional business opportunities.

An important basis for successfully conducted projects is the continuous incorporation of **customer feedback** – also in early project stages. In the context of quarries, the role of the customer is varying. On the one hand, a technology provider might be in a B2B relationship with a quarrying company which in turn is aimed at the actual end users of the product, e.g. quarry workers.

We emphasize that continuous feedback from customers and/or end users is important; however, there are specific moments where a detailed customer review and feedback loop is mandatory from our point of view:

- **Product ideation:** find out and analyse the customers' needs and pain points (e.g. the need of an easy-to-operate, reliable object detection and warning component in a quarrying scraper system), work out the benefits over existing solutions (also on the external market) together with the customers.
 - **Product design:** validate and align the final product plan with the customers' needs and expectations.
 - **Minimum viable products (MVPs), Proofs of concept (POCs):** gather feedback on early basic versions of the product with the most important features implemented. A "beta testing" group of end users might provide the most valuable feedback at this point.
 - **In operation:** With a large group of actual users, additional needs and pain points might arise. It is important to take action to maintain high customer satisfaction.
- (2) **Project horizontals:** We follow a horizontal project structure consisting of several topic clusters, e.g.:
 - a. **Quality and Project Management:** concerned with procedural, regulatory and commercial tasks.
 - b. **Artificial Intelligence:** concerned with machine learning model development and optimization.
 - c. **Data:** concerned with data generation, storage, access and processing.
 - d. **Software/Hardware:** concerned with software/hardware development and integration.

Figure 7: Technological roadmap to safety AI development.

We now outline our recommendations for the different project stages more in detail.

4.2.1 Design phase

The design phase mainly is concerned with project setup, building competence and making important design considerations. With a foresighted planning, arising risks in later project phases can already be mitigated.

Project management process setup: besides standard project setup (e.g. commercial, milestone and resource planning), a decision on the collaboration model for product development is necessary. From our point of view, an agile collaboration model fits best to the dynamic environment of AI/Data/Software. Dividing the project team into different horizontals (e.g. as shown in the roadmap above), depending on the size of the project, a scaled agile collaboration model (such as the *Scaled Agile Framework® (SAFe®)*) can be the best solution to achieve maximum effectiveness and efficiency by establishing clear responsibilities and interfaces.

Quality management process setup: in highly regulated environments like safety-critical applications, quality management is crucial. The new regulations on AI and data processing require additional effort which must be taken into consideration in advance. A typical project risk arises by trivializing the need for quality management and piling up quality debt during the project. Therefore, we propose to put clear quality management processes, together with the corresponding roles, into place. In general, for product development, frameworks such as the *Software Process Improvement and Capability Determination (SPICE, cf. ISO/IEC TS 33061:2021)* might be helpful. In daily business, software and AI developers as well as data engineers need efficient and agreed guidelines for development, test and review. Regarding functional safety aspects, a procedural standard considering safety integrity levels (SILs, e.g. cf. IEC 61508) and derived development guidelines (e.g. MISRA) can provide an adequate framework, also in conjunction with risk assessment (see below).

AI literacy: by definition (cf. EU AI Act Art. 3(56)), *AI literacy* “means skills, knowledge and understanding that allow ... taking into account their respective rights and obligations ..., to make an informed deployment of AI systems, as well as to gain awareness about the opportunities and risks of AI and possible harm it can cause.” Depending on the specific role, technical in-depth knowledge or a more high-level, management-orientated view on AI is necessary to avoid risks like underestimation of the effort needed for a safely running AI system or setting too high expectations on AI capabilities for the intended solution. On the other hand, AI literacy can be a booster for innovation by allowing for more ideas in business

development. Here the interaction between the different stakeholders becomes crucial again, as it provides also a cross-organizational learning opportunity.

Regulatory expertise: In context of the EU AI Act, AI literacy goes hand in hand with the up-to-date knowledge of relevant legislation and standards. In a digitized quarrying environment, many use cases are conceivable, and thus many different regulations (e.g. for vehicles or machines) can be in scope. Therefore, building up and using regulatory expertise in early project stage is crucial to take into account all arising requirements and obligations. As for AI literacy, it might be sensible to have experts with in-depth knowledge as well as basic expertise through or the project or company.

Scope assessment: with regulatory expertise, it is needed to analyse the applicability of the various regulations (e.g. AI Act, Data act, harmonized safety regulations) to the project at hand. As a result, it will be clear what the specific requirements for the development and operation of the desired product are. This lays the foundation for important design decisions in the design phase as well as for the setup of development, testing and operations toolchains at the beginning of the implementation phase, and will constitute a roadmap in itself throughout the project and product lifecycle.

Risk assessment: besides standard risk assessment procedures in project management, safety AI requires a more in-detail assessment of the safety-criticality of the intended AI system, since the requirements arising from the classification as high-risk AI are far greater than for non-high-risk AI systems. Together with the use of safety integrity levels for components, one can again make important design decisions (to e.g. reassess a high-risk classification) at an early project stage. Missing a crucial detail can lead to higher costs later and shall thus be avoided.

Design considerations: using the results from scope and risk assessment as guidelines, design considerations can be undertaken resulting in a more detailed project plan. Taking into account the needs of the horizontal teams like AI, Data or Software, the transition from design to implementation phase is done. At the latest now, agile structures should exist, leading to the planning of the first product increment (PI).

4.2.2 Implementation phase

Naturally, the implementation phase is concerned with the actual product development. In a highly regulated setting, our objective to have a certified safety AI system has to be reached prior to the placing on the market. For the actual product development, we propose a **DevOps** approach for the project horizontals. In our opinion, this approach provides the best fit to agile frameworks on the one hand, but also to the possibly arising regulatory obligations on the other hand.

DevOps, DataOps, MLOps: Overall, *DevOps*, a combination of *development* and *operations* practices, offers significant benefits for industrial enterprises. Adopting DevOps can lead to enhanced productivity, reduced operational costs, decision-making capabilities and greater innovation, positioning industrial enterprises for success in a competitive environment. In particular, *DataOps*, or *Data Operations*, is an agile approach to data management that focuses on improving the quality, speed, and reliability of data analytics and data-driven decision-making. Regarding AI, *MLOps*, or *Machine Learning Operations*, is aimed at effective leverage of machine learning (ML). A common characteristic of these approaches is streamlining processes by automation.

Figure 8: ML/Data/DevOps pipeline for development and operation of AI systems.

The use of toolchains to automate and streamline processes such as testing, integration, deployment, data workflows or machine learning development offers various benefits:

- **Enhanced collaboration:** By promoting collaboration between development (e.g. system development, data engineering, data science), business stakeholders and IT operations teams, DevOps practices enhance communication and foster a culture of shared responsibility, breaking down silos and aligning everyone on objectives and processes.
- **Faster iteration cycles:** Streamlined processes and automation lead to faster system development cycles and quicker deployment of applications and machine learning models, as well as accelerated delivery of data insights. This allows for quicker decision-making and responsiveness to market changes. Additionally, continuous integration and continuous delivery (CI/CD) practices enable teams to deliver updates and new features more frequently, improving overall product quality and user satisfaction.
- **Higher quality and performance:** Quality is also improved by the reduction of human error due to automation. Through systematic experimentation and monitoring, MLOps helps in identifying the best-performing models and techniques, leading to improved outcomes and business insights.
- **Continuous monitoring and maintenance:** With MLOps, models can be continuously monitored for performance and accuracy. This allows for timely updates and retraining, ensuring that models remain relevant and effective over time. DataOps emphasizes continuous monitoring and validation of data, which helps to ensure high data quality and integrity. This leads to more reliable analytics and better business outcomes. DevOps also encourages a feedback-driven approach, where monitoring and performance metrics are used to identify and resolve issues proactively. This results in improved system performance and reduced downtime.
- **Enhanced governance and compliance:** By implementing robust governance and compliance measures, DataOps helps to mitigate risks associated with data management, ensuring that data usage adheres to regulatory standards and best practices. MLOps frameworks often include features for tracking model lineage, versioning, and compliance with regulatory standards. DevOps frameworks usually come together with measures for cybersecurity providing a safeguard for product development.
- **Scalability:** As data volumes and model complexity grow, the tools and frameworks necessary to manage and optimize these processes without compromising performance are at hand.
- **Cost efficiency:** By optimizing resource usage, reducing manual intervention and mitigation of the risk of human error, the described DevOps approaches provide a cost-efficient concept for smart product development.

Naturally, the setup of the respective toolchains and processes takes place at the beginning of implementation. From a regulatory point of view (cf. EU Data Act), this might also be mandatory because, e.g. data risks (such as data bias) have to be mitigated right from the start.

Certification requirements: With a DevOps-focussed approach, many of the risks described in legislation can be mitigated at once, providing a huge step towards certification. Nevertheless, depending on the outcome of the scope and risk assessments from the product design phase, additional certification requirements (e.g. putting up a declaration of conformity, assessment by a notified body) have to be fulfilled prior to the placing on the market.

4.2.3 Deployment phase

In deployment phase, when the product is available on the market and put into service, the horizontal DevOps activities continue. For instance, necessary updates have to be conducted, functions are extended based on the customers' feedback, product performance is monitored. These activities go hand in hand with management activities.

Monitoring: In addition to the technical monitoring carried out by the DevOps toolchains, product surveillance in operation is necessary. Arising incidents have to be addressed in a timely manner. Again, relying on tool-based processes will support here.

Request handling: In the cases where data regulations such as the EU Data Act or the GDPR are in scope, users or third parties can file requests upon data access or data processing. Moreover, requests by notified bodies or legal institutions might arise and have to be handled. Once more, with effectively design data processes, responding to these requests will be cost-efficient.

Re-use considerations: Obtaining higher amounts of user feedback and general market surveillance can lead to further product and feature ideas. At this stage, it is necessary to foster re-use by sharing and documentation of knowledge, considering data reuse and performing lessons learned meetings.

4.3 Summary

The goal of this deliverable has been to answer the question "What needs to be done so that AI can be used in quarries for safety-critical applications?". To this end, we provided a strategic roadmap for safety AI development and shared insights on relevant legislation on AI and Data. The conducted stakeholder interviews additionally allow for understanding actual pain points regarding the development and use of digitized, smart products in quarrying business.

In a nutshell, our major findings and key messages are as follows:

- The basis is constituted by **trust** and **acceptance** of AI (by quarrying workers and managers) and **recognition** of its capabilities in safety-critical use cases.
- Since the fields of AI, Data and Safety are complex and dynamically evolving, gaining and maintaining **up-to-date knowledge** (about technical and legal topics) is one central milestone for quarrying companies and technology providers towards a successfully certified safety-critical AI system for use in quarries.
- **Cost-efficiency** can be reached in the long run by **streamlined** quality management and development processes, even though the initial transformation efforts might be high.
- **Collaboration** of all relevant stakeholders such as quarrying companies, technology providers, educational institutions and policy makers is the key element to reach an effective and efficient use of the huge capabilities of intelligent systems in the quarrying ecosystem.

List of Figures

Figure 1: Layers of regulation.	9
Figure 2: Main findings and recommendations from the EU AI Act.	14
Figure 3: Main findings and recommendations from the EU Data Act.	16
Figure 4: Main findings and recommendations from the EU Cyber Resilience Act.	17
Figure 5: Main findings and recommendations from the GDPR.	19
Figure 6: Social roadmap targeting safety AI development.	23
Figure 7: Technological roadmap to safety AI development.	26
Figure 8: ML/Data/DevOps pipeline for development and operation of AI systems.	28

List of Tables

Table 1. Deliverables with activities regarding occupational safety.	8
Table 2. Legislative acts adopted by the EU with respect to data, AI and digital products.	10
Table 3. Scope of the EU AI Act.	12
Table 4. Definition and risk classification of AI in connection with the regulations contained in the AI Act.	12
Table 5. Requirements for providers and deployers according to the AI Act.	13
Table 6. Core regulations for manufacturers, data holders and users contained in the Data Act.	15
Table 7. Criticality classification (cf. CRA Arts. 7,8, Annexes III,IV) and impact on conformity assessment procedure (cf. CRA Art. 32).	17
Table 8. Principles relating to processing of personal data (cf. GDPR Art. 5(1)).	18
Table 9. Rights of the data subject (cf. GDPR Ch. III).	18
Table 10. Core data principles.	19
Table 11. Regulatory affairs and quality management.	20

List of References

DigiEcoQuarry Consortium (2023). *Deliverable 3.6 Recognition system for workers nearby mobile and quarrying machinery.*

DigiEcoQuarry Consortium (2024a). *Deliverable 4.3 Report on the AI Algorithms and Services*

DigiEcoQuarry Consortium (2024b). *Deliverable 5.1 SW/HW full solution to mitigate collision avoidance risks*

Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act)

Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act)

Regulation (EU) 2024/... of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013 and (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Cyber Resilience Act)

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

Directive (EU) 2024/... of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on liability for defective products and repealing Council Directive 85/374/EEC

Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on adapting non-contractual civil liability rules to artificial intelligence (AI Liability Directive)

Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act)

Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act)

Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act)

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ISO/IEC TS 33061:2021 Information technology — Process assessment — Process assessment model for software life cycle processes.

IEC 61508:2010 Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems.

[MISRA](#), Motor Industry Software Reliability Association (MISRA).